

Further testing of a yield loss simulation model for rice in different production situations

II. FOCUS ON WATER-STRESSED ENVIRONMENTS

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A recently developed yield loss simulation model for rice pests was tested under the different production situations (PSs) of South Asia and Southeast (Willocquet et al 1998, 1999). The work reported here aimed at testing this model under a reference PS (PS2) used in experiments done at different sites, and under a second PS (PS4) not yet addressed in previous work, where the crop experiences high water stress. Deadhearts and whiteheads caused by stem borers and weeds were considered as common rice pests that can cause yield losses in tropical Asia (Savary et al 1998).

An experiment was done at IRRI during the 1998 dry season. The approach used to calibrate and test the model, the experimental layout, and the field procedures applied were the same as those described in Willocquet et al (1999 p 25, this volume). Two PSs were addressed: PS2

(IR72 transplanted with young seedlings, 110 kg N ha⁻¹, irrigated rice) and PS4 (IR64 transplanted with young seedlings, 110 kg N ha⁻¹, rainfed crop). Five injury treatments were addressed in each PS: weed infestation (WD), deadhearts (DH), whiteheads (WH), the combination of the three injuries (COMBI), and the noninjured treatment (CTRL).

The simulation of attainable organ growth, tiller dynamics, and final yield was close to the actual observation (see figure) in the two PSs considered. The dry weights of leaves and panicles were very sensitive to varying PSs: the maximum values were highest in PS2 and lowest in PS4 (shortage of water and/or N). Final panicle yield was 150 g m⁻² in PS4 and 800 g m⁻² in PS2.

The table gives simulated and observed grain yields for the 10 (PS × injury) combinations addressed in the experi-

ment. An acceptance interval of ± 10% in the observed yield was defined to assess simulated yield outputs. The model simulated yields within this acceptance interval in all but two cases (PS2, WEED and COMBI treatments). The model overestimated yield losses caused by weeds in PS2.

The model simulated attainable growth and yield adequately under these two contrasting PSs. This modeling approach thus enables us to simulate damage mechanisms in contrasting PSs. In general, the yield-reducing effects of the different pests addressed are well accounted for by the model (see table).

References

- Savary S, Elazegui FA, Willocquet L, Teng PS. 1998. Changing production situations in rice and implications for plant pathology. Paper presented at the International Conference of Plant Pathology, 9–16 Aug 1998, Edinburgh.

Attainable rice growth in two PSs: observed (dots) ±SEM and simulated (plain line) dry weight (g m⁻²) of roots (ROOTW), dry weight of leaves (LEAFW), dry weight of stems (STEMW), dry weight of panicles (PANW), and number (m⁻²) of tillers (TOTIL). Observed data were collected from control plots in the experiment done at IRRI in 1998 (A:PS2, B:PS4) (see text for details).

Simulated and observed grain yields (g m⁻²), IRRI, 1998.

Treatment ^a	PS2 ^b		PS4	
	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated
CTRL	704	696	94	91
DH	686	676	90	93
WH	637	621	100	90
WEED	571	470 ^c	61	59
COMBI	525	413 ^c	52	57

^aCTRL = control, DH = deadhearts, WH = whiteheads, WEED = weed infestation, COMBI = combination of the three injuries. ^bPS2 = reference production situation, PS4 = production situation with high water stress. ^cSimulated grain yield outside the acceptance interval ($\pm 10\%$ of observed grain yield).

Willoquet L, Savary S, Fernandez L, Elazegui F, Teng PS. 1998. Simulation of yield losses caused by rice diseases, insects, and weeds in tropical Asia. IRRI Discuss. Pap. Ser. 34. Willocquet L, Fernandez L, Singh HM, Srivastava RK, Rizvi SMA, Savary S. 1999. Further testing of a yield loss simulation model for rice in different production situations. 1. Focus on rice-wheat system environments. Int. Rice Res. Notes 24(2):25-27.

4th International Rice Genetics Symposium set for October 2000

The Fourth International Rice Genetics Symposium (IRGS) will be held at IRRI on 22-27 October 2000. The first IRGS was held in 1985. It led to the birth of the Rice Genetics Cooperative (RGC), which aimed to promote international cooperation in rice genetics. The same year, the Rockefeller Foundation organized the International Program on Rice Biotechnology, which has played a major role in advancing the frontiers of rice science, international collaboration, and human resource development in rice. During the second IRGS (held in 1990), a unified numbering system for rice chromosomes and linkage groups was established. More than 500 scientists from 31 countries participated in the third IRGS (held in 1995). Correct orientation of classical and molecular linkage maps was one of the symposium highlights.

Major advances in the genetics and molecular biology of rice have become apparent during the past 15 years. A high-density molecular genetic map of more than 2,300 DNA markers has been developed and several genes of economic importance as well as quantitative trait loci (QTL) have been tagged with molecular markers. Synteny relationships between genomes of rice and several other cereals have been established. Molecular marker-aided selection is being used to move genes from one varietal background to another and to pyramid genes. Scientists have developed BAC and YAC libraries and are using them in the physical mapping of the rice genome. A map-based cloning strategy has been used to isolate agronomically important genes. Regeneration from protoplasts of many indica and japonica varieties has allowed researchers to introduce novel genes into elite germplasm through transformation. More recently, biolistic and *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation procedures have become available. International programs on rice genome sequencing and functional genomics have been established. These developments have opened new frontiers in rice molecular biology, particularly for understanding the genetic architecture of traits and their manipulation, modifying gene expression, genome sequencing, functional genomics, and gene discovery. Researchers are using these breakthroughs to develop rice varieties with higher yield potential and yield stability for feeding 50% more rice consumers by 2025.

The fourth IRGS will feature plenary sessions, oral presentations, and poster sessions. Participants will discuss the latest developments in rice systematics and evolution, cytogenetics, classical genetics, tissue and cell culture, molecular markers, genetic engineering, and genomics. The proceedings will be published.

Scientists interested in attending the symposium should send a registration form indicating their name, academic title, address (phone, fax, email), and tentative presentation title to Dr. G.S. Khush at IRRI, MCPO Box 3127, Makati City 1271, Philippines (fax: 0063-2-761-2404; email: g.khush@cgiar.org or to Dr. T. Kinoshita, Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University, Kita 9, Nishi 9, Sapporo 060, Japan (fax: 0081-11-706-4934; email: Takamura@abs.agr.hokudai.ac.jp).

Important dates

- 31 October 1999 - Deadline for submission of registration forms
- 1 April 2000 - Deadline for abstracts
- 30 June 2000 - Deadline for full papers

The members of the organizing committee are J. Bennett, D.S. Brar, S.K. Datta, B. Hardy, M.T. Jackson, G.S. Khush, H. Leung, and Z. Li.

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